

Content Analysis Of Social Studies Of Class V With Reference To Character Education

Muhamad Jamil, Nasrullah, Ziarab Mahmood, Safdar Hussain

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 10, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Character Education, Social Studies, Character building</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5671536</p>	<p><i>The research is conducted to analyze the content of Punjab text book Social Studies for class V with reference to Character Education. The content of the Social Study requires to investigate for particular context to inculcate the character values among the students. Character education is very important to establish a peaceful environment in the country. The educational system of Pakistan is providing only information to the students and the part of character development is overlooked. Now it is realized the importance of character education by the stake holders , thinkers, the intellectuals, the policy makers, the teachers and society. The objective of the study was to identify the content about character education in social Study Text Book for class V published by the Punjab Text Book Board Lahore for year 2020-2021. It is qualitative research and the content analysis technique was used. The analysis shows that the text book of Social Study for class V needs some improvements in some area with reference to character education.</i></p>

Introduction

Lickona (1989) has explained that Character is a value in action. He says that character has three parts i.e. moral knowing, moral feeling and moral behavior. Good character is always knowing the good, doing the good and desiring the good. Character is rooted in heart and mind and displayed through actions. Similarly Katilmis et al. (2011, p. 854) commented as "Good character is a concept which contains knowing good, embracing good and doing well". John Dewey stated that, "Character as interpenetration of habits" (as cited Althof&Berkiwitz, 1999, p.497). Homiak (2007) said character is our distinctive mark that differentiates ourselves from others. In present era character education has least priority of the stakeholders. It is also true that the importance and the need of character education increase.

Education develops the roots of nation. Education prepares generations according to their ideological, cultural, social and religious norms through education. Present social evils like corruption, bribery, hoarding, smuggling and adulteration are spreading in society. The importance and need of character education increased. Character education, moral education and values educations are inter changeably used terms having same meanings.

Britzman and Hanson (2005) identified the six pillars of character education. These values are acceptable to every society. Each pillar is a comprehensive term and included the principles and ethical values. These pillars are trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness, caring and citizenship. The present research elaborates the content of Social Studies Text Book with reference to above components of character education.

Character education is a systematic process of instilling values and virtues in students, oneself, fellow human beings, the environment, and nationality that manifests in thoughts, attitudes, feelings, words, and deeds based on religious norms, law, manners, culture, and customs (Marini, 2017). The common belief of character education from psychological and philosophical perspectives is that virtues can be taught and learned through the proper pedagogy (Cooley, 2008). Hoge (2012) describes character education as a way of adjusting the behaviors of the students in order to become good citizens of the future.

Berkowitz and Bier (2005) suggested for an effective implementation of character education included providing professional development, increasing interaction among peers, integrating character education into the school curriculum including direct teaching about character. Yaksel (2005) indicated the school culture and its relationship act as a hidden curriculum in development of character among students. He added that the attention of teacher on formal curriculum, textbook and other material create the moral atmosphere helps in moral development. Marshal et al., (2011) indicated that character education is perpetually believed, to some kind of ways through which the students are being nurtured in the direction of seeing things in different perspectives and provide them training in changing situation.

Quran says "And verily, for you Muhammad (PBUH) is (standard of) character". Prophet PBUH said "I have sent to perfect, good character" (68:4, AlQalam). Akhlaq (Moral) education is part of Islamic education

which has its own teaching model to the students. Character building is a vital part of Islamic education. Islam gives us clear ethical values of life. It is the need of hour to prepare young children in such a way that they reflect all the values which are symbol of Islamic society.

Handbook of character education (2010) enlists five key points for a successful program of character building:

- Planned instruction
- Application
- Teacher-friendly attitude
- Support of staff of the institution
- Preparation of students

Aynur (2011) indicated that character education should include the curriculum of early classes to build a strong foundation of future generations. Anderson (2000) has emphasized upon the re-introduction of character education. Romanowski (2005) suggested that the ultimate responsibility of the school is to develop an environment in which reinforces bright sides of students learning and behavior, there by students also practicing those good values they learned from the character education program. After Early child hood education (ECE) the primary level of education is suitable to inculcate the character values in the students. Aynur (2011) stated that it is important to set a strong foundation of positive character during the earlier grades and to reinforce and build upon that foundation during the later grades.

This research analyze all the factors and recommends measures to take steps for right direction and preparation of pedagogy for the future needs. The purpose of this study is to analyze the content of Islamic Studies in the context of character education. Character education has always been encouraging, solidly, and continually preparing the leaders of tomorrow. Character education helps students to develop important human qualities such as justice, diligence, respect, and courage, and to understand why it is important to live by them. It promotes character development through the exploration of ethical issues across the curriculum.

Aristotle's Theory of moral virtue and Thomas Likona's models provide the theoretical framework of this research. The early Greek philosophers Plato and Aristotle said that good character is a gateway to harmony, justice and happiness for all. Aristotle considers character education as highest virtue. Philosophers and thinkers emphasizes upon the character education of the young generations. The promising ground of bring the framework of character education is to "make critical links between the lessons of greater social sympathy in the classroom and benevolent action in life" (Cooley, 2008, p. 203).

In this research the content analysis shows that the content is included for character education traits but in some areas needs improvement . Conclusion and recommendations are given for the character education of the students at primary level. The primary level is very important for the personality development learning of character traits .of a child. The class V students are of the early age group 10 to 12 years who are near to teen age group. To learn the value education, character components and develop a positive sense in a child this is most appropriate period.

OBJECTIVE

To identify the content of the Text Book of Social Study for Class V that Promotes Character Education.

METHODOLOGY

This study was qualitative in nature. Text book of social Study for class V developed by Ministry of Education Curriculum Wing and published by Punjab Textbook board was analyzed using qualitative analysis. The study was carried out by the techniques of content analysis. The present study describes the content analysis with reference to character education.

DATA ANALYSIS

The content of Social Studies minutely analyzed. The objectives of Social Studies text book for Grade V were as follows:-

- Provide historical information to the student
- To reflect the cultural norms of Pakistani society
- To become a good citizen

Social Studies Punjab Text Book (2020-2021)

Social studies book contains eight chapters. Book is divided in the three main headings Geography, History and Culture. The material under heading of culture analyzed for Character Education. The analysis was based on the statement of Britzman and Hanson (2005) who identify the six pillars of character education. These values are acceptable to every society. Each pillar is a comprehensive term and included the principles and ethical values. **These pillars are trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness, caring, and citizenship.** The content of social studies book V analyzed in (Annexure A).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The purpose of the study was to investigate and analyze the content of Social Studies text book of Grade V regarding character education. To achieve the objectives the researcher critically analyzed the content of Social Studies text books.

Following conclusions were drawn.

1. The objectives of curriculum included the component of Character Education. It can be inferred that the Social Studies chapter vi and vii indicated the ethical values that are not fulfilling the needs of the society regarding character education.
2. It was concluded that sufficient material of character education is need to be included in the curriculum of social studies of grade v to fulfill the need of the society.
3. It is also revealed that the curriculum of social studies is in a continuous sequential process which includes every aspect and the component of character education but more clarification is needed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following recommendations are given.

1. More material should be included with reference to character education in the text books of primary level so that we inculcate the positive character among the students in this particular age level.
2. More examples should be included in the lessons for the proper propagation of moral duties of an individual.
3. More attention should be given on the teachers training programs so that teachers feel the importance of character education and having skills to nourish the students with positive character.

Acknowledgements or Notes

It is to ensure to the editors, that the research work is our personal input. Neither this article or its any part is published anywhere nor in submitted for publication. If anything is found against the rule and research ethics, we are responsible and this journal is not responsible at all.

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Author Information

Muhammad Jamil

Ph D scholar
Department of Education
University of Wah, Pakistan

Dr. Nasrullah

Assistant Professor
University of Wah, Pakistan

Dr. Ziarab Mahmood (Corresponding Author)**Assistant Professor**

Mohi-ud-Din Islamic University
Nerian Sharif AJ&K, Pakistan

Dr. Safdar Hussain

Teacher
Punjab Education Department
Pakistan
